

AI-Based Complex for Measurement and Control Using the Machine Learning Method

Azad Bayramov, Samir Suleymanov, Fatali Abdullayev and Rauf Muradov
Republican Seismic Survey Center of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences

ABSTRACT

In recent years, seismologists and geophysicists have found new evidence that levels of radioactive radon gas in and above the soil, as well as the strength of the Earth's magnetic field in a local region, can effectively act as earthquake triggers. Given the relevance of this problem, this paper presents the results of development and research of an autonomous (robotic) measurement control complex based on Artificial Intelligence using the Machine Learning method. The complex is designed for simultaneous measurement of the concentration level of radioactive radon gas in the near-surface layer and at a depth of 1-3 meters underground, the level of the Earth's magnetic field intensity with simultaneous analysis of seismic processes in the territory of Azerbaijan and neighboring regions. While measuring the magnetic field strength, solar activity is simultaneously analyzed. GPRS radio communication modem was developed to ensure communication with the Internet, to apply the machine learning method and communicate with the center. The purpose of the development and research is to study the correlations of measured values with seismic activity. A software algorithm has been developed to control the complex and carry out measurements.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Control System, Machine Learning, Radon, Magnetic Field Strength, Algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of seismic activity and the identification of its relationships with parameters measured on the Earth's surface is an important task in seismology. Over the past decades, scientists have attempted to develop methods for predicting earthquakes. Particular attention is paid to the search for precursors, among which radon anomalies and magnetic field variations stand out as potentially significant. In addition, growing computing power and the development of artificial intelligence methods open up new possibilities for analyzing complex multifactorial data [1].

Current research highlights the need for complex systems capable of collecting, processing and interpreting information in real time. This is especially relevant for regions with high seismic activity, such as the Caucasus region. The development of autonomous systems capable of operating in remote and hard-to-reach areas is becoming a key area of modern seismology. Such systems allow real-time monitoring without human intervention, minimizing risks and increasing response speed.

Historically, earthquake forecasting has relied on empirical observations and statistical models. However, the high complexity and nonlinearity of geophysical processes require more flexible methods that can adapt to changing conditions. To predict earthquakes, analyze large value of data, and identify patterns in geodynamic processes, the effective methods such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) are widely used [2].

Many scientific papers are devoted to the study of seismic activity in the Earth's interior and the analysis of correlations between the parameters of this phenomenon and various processes whose characteristics can be measured on the Earth's surface [3]. The aim of

these studies is to study the possible short-term forecast of earthquakes. The solving these problems is difficult because this task is multifactorial. In such tasks, when assessing risk, it is necessary to take into account many terrestrial and cosmic factors that affect seismicity and the structure of the Earth's crust.

It should be taken into account that in order to increase the reliability of the assessment, it is necessary to consider the mutual correlations between the factors. The risk under consideration depends on many geodynamic factors that are individual for each separate area of the Earth's surface. Based on this assumption, in [1], an analysis of a multifactor model for seismological research was performed.

In recent years, Artificial Intelligence methods have been used to study these phenomena in depth in the hope of finding a more or less correct solution to this problem [4,5]. These methods include various areas: Machine Learning, Deep Learning, neural network method, Wavelet transform, etc. This article presents the results of development and research of an autonomous detector control complex based on Artificial Intelligence using the Machine Learning method. The purpose of the development is to study the correlations of measured values with seismic activity. A software algorithm for controlling the complex and taking measurements has been developed.

2. METHOD OF MACHINE LEARNING

For solving a specific problem scientists use algorithms, that is, systems of sequential operations. The result accuracy of processing the input data depends on algorithm required for each specific problem. The method can be used to assess the real state of the problem. It is necessary to run the algorithm to solve this problem.

Machine Learning method, being an effective tool of Artificial Intelligence, is intended for the development of optimal algorithms in various fields of science and technology. These algorithms are improved (in other words, can learn) using various databases and information taken from the Internet. Depending on the volume and complexity of the data being processed, machine learning methods are classified into the following types:

- Supervised Learning method, it is used when a machine learns to recognize objects (signals) or to decipher information, in this case the test (supervised) system is trained using “stimulus-response” examples;
- Unsupervised Learning, this method is based on the principle of "this object is similar to other objects". In this case, the algorithms of this method study the properties of objects (images), detect and recognize distinctive (unusual) anomalies in objects (images). In this machine learning method, a mathematical algorithm is trained on data that indefinitely points to the correct solution (or category) of a problem or task. In this case, the algorithm itself determines patterns, structures, images, and, including, correlations in the data;
- Reinforcement Learning method, this method is used when the machine must perform tasks in an external environment, and in these cases the actions performed may have many variations. This is a method of machine learning. Here, the test system (in other words, agent) learns by investigation a certain state of environment. The reply of the environment to the decisions made are reinforcement signals. Such reinforcement learning is a special case of learning. Here, the test system (in other words, agent) learns by investigation a certain state of environment. The reply of the environment to the decisions made are reinforcement signals. Such reinforcement learning is a special case of learning with a teacher (in this case, the environment or its model).

The algorithms used to solve problems can be classified into two classes:

- 1) learning algorithms which are used for classification, clustering, regression, etc., to solve forecasting problems in statistical problems;
- 2) Neural Networks and Deep Learning, which are used for recognizing objects or patterns or generating images, as well as for control or decision making, automatic computer translation and other similar complex tasks.

It is possible to combine several different approaches into ensembles of Machine Learning models.

Below, there are the most popular classical Machine Learning modes:

- Random Forest, this method uses an ensemble of decision trees;
- support vector machine (SVM), used to solve grading and involution problems. The distinctive idea of this method is to construct a hyperplane. This hyperplane separates the pattern objects in an optimal way;
- k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) nonparametric algorithm which is supervised machine learning method, it used for classification and regression. It works by identifying the k closest features to a new feature in the feature space and predicting the label of the new feature based on the labels of these nearest neighbors;
- linear regression;
- Bayesian classification method is a probabilistic approach that uses probability to represent uncertainty about relationships extracted from data, updating previous beliefs using posterior distributions to make optimal decisions;
 - gradient boosting (XGBoost, LightGBM), is a machine learning technique that builds forecasting models by sequentially combining weak training models, usually Random Forest method [6]. XGBoost and LightGBM - they implement gradient boosting, each with its own characteristics. XGBoost stands out for its performance and regularization, while LightGBM stands out for its speed and efficiency when working with large amounts of data;
- neural networks and deep learning methods
- methods for finding association rules.

Reinforcement learning is effective in tasks of controlling filter parameters and adapting algorithms to changing environmental conditions. The Q-learning method is one of the key algorithms and is used to determine optimal actions based on rewards obtained during the learning process. Modifications such as Deep Q-Learning and DDPG (Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient) are also relevant.

Adaptive Heuristic Critic (AHC), SARSA and Q-learning are the examples of methods. For an example, let consider Q-learning process. It includes [6,7]:

- states set;
- actions set;
- reward function;
- transition function;
- learning rate (usually 0.1), at that, the higher it is, the more an agent trusts new information;
- discounting factor, the lower it is, the less an agent “thinks” about the benefits of its actions in future [6].

Neural networks (NN), or artificial neural networks (ANN) are one of the types of machine learning. Neural networks are used as an algorithm for machine vision and

translation, speech recognition, music, and image processing. A machine learning method based on neural networks is called Deep learning.

3 AI-BASED COMPLEXES FOR MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL

The concentration of radioactive radon gas and the intensity of the Earth's magnetic field are taken as the measured physical quantities. Therefore, at the first stage, only two types of detectors were developed: for radon gas and the Earth's magnetic field.

The developed complex consists of detector units, an interface, a control unit, an Internet channel unit, a unit for receiving data from a seismic center, a unit for receiving data on the current state of solar activity, an analysis unit based on Artificial Intelligence and decision making, and an autonomous power supply unit on solar panels. The detector units include a radon radioactive gas detector and magnetometer devices to measure the magnetic field strength in a given area.

It is known that solar activity has a strong impact on the Earth's magnetic field. Therefore, when studying the state of the magnetic field, its correlation with solar activity should be taken into account [8].

In simplified form, the algorithm of the software for control and analysis of the complex consists of the following main blocks interacting with each other. This algorithm is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Simplified diagram of the algorithm of the software for control and analysis of the complex

There are next units (blocks) in Figure 1:

- unit 1 for receiving, filtering and processing data on radon concentration on the earth's surface and at a depth of 1-3 meters;
- unit 2 for receiving data from a magnetometer;

The central element of the circuit is the SIM900A integrated circuit - a communication chip that supports quad-band GSM networks and provides interaction with an external microcontroller via a UART interface:

- The UART module is connected to the microcontroller via (Tx, Rx) signals;
- PWKEY, STATUS, NETLIGHT control lines are used to control and visually monitor the operating mode of the modem.

SIM card interface (U9).

The SIM card connection is placed in a separate interface block. This interface includes the following signals:

- SIM_VDD – power line,
- SIM_RST – reset signal,
- SIM_CLK – clock signal,
- SIM_DATA – duplex data line,
- SIM_PRE – presence signal.

These lines are connected to the SIM card tray through protective resistors and TVS diodes in series, protecting them from both electromagnetic influence and static charge.

Power cycle.

The module is powered by an LDO stabilizer type MIC29302WU. The use of this stabilizer allows you to reduce the voltage of 5 V to 4 V required for SIM900.

- Filtering of high-frequency pulses is ensured by the use of electrolytic and ceramic capacitors (100 μ F and 100 nF) at the input and output;
- The power circuitry protects the module from current peaks and can provide the \sim 2A instantaneous current required during GPRS data transfer.

To monitor the operating modes of the module, two main LEDs are used:

- STATUS LED – displays the general operating status of the module,
- NETLIGHT LED – indicates the registration status in the GSM network.

Both LEDs are controlled by NPN transistors (BC547B), which isolate the signal lines from the voltage level in the module, increasing reliability..

The PWKEY signal is controlled by a transistor switch to turn the module on and off using software. This approach is effective both in automated systems and in devices that require energy conservation.

The RF output of SIM900 is connected to the GSM network via the external SMA antenna connector (RF1). The antenna unit ensures stable reception and transmission of the module signal.

The developed circuit diagram is distinguished by a stable power supply, SIM card interface protection mechanisms, operating mode control via LED indicators and GPRS functionality. This solution is suitable for widespread use in data acquisition and remote monitoring systems, IoT devices and wireless control applications.

SIM900 is a GSM/GPRS module developed by SIMCom. Through this module, microcontrollers can connect to the cellular network and perform the following functions:

- Making and receiving calls;
- Send and receive SMS;
- Connect to the Internet via GPRS (2G);
- Data transmission via TCP/IP protocol.

Main technical characteristics:

- Network support: GSM 850/900/1800/1900 MHz (quad-band)
- Supply voltage: 3.2 – 4.8 V (optimal 4.0 V)

- Current consumption of electric current:
 - Standby mode: ~10 mA;
 - During a conversation: ~250 mA;
 - Peak current: up to 2 A.
 - Controlled by AT commands (via UART).
 - UART interface: data transfer rate is in range of 9600 ÷ 115200 baud.
- Dimensions: approximately 24x24 mm (the chips themselves), and the modules (boards) are approximately 40x40 mm.

AT commands and their use for SIM900 module.

AT commands (Attention commands) are standardized text commands used to communicate with GSM/GPRS modules via UART interface. With these commands, SIM900 allows you to manage calls, SMS, GPRS Internet, TCP/IP and other services. AT commands usually start with the AT prefix and are returned by the module as an OK (command accepted) or ERROR (command not executed) response. The main diagnostic commands are presented in Table 1.

THE MAIN DIAGNOSTIC COMMANDS

Commands	Explanation	Example/Answer
AT	Checks the working status of the module	Answer: OK
AT+CPIN?	Checks the status of the SIM card	Answer: +CPIN: READY
AT+CSQ	Measures the signal level (values from 0 to 31)	Answer: +CSQ: 20, 0
AT+CREG?	Network registration status	Answer: +CREG: 0, 1 (Upon registration)

Table 1. AT main diagnostic commands

GPRS/Internet connection

Main sequence:

1. Setting up GPRS parameters
 AT+SAPBR=3,1,"CONTYPE","GPRS"
 AT+SAPBR=3,1,"APN","internet"
2. Open connection
 AT+SAPBR=1,1
3. Checking the connection
 AT+SAPBR=2,1
 +SAPBR: 1,1,"10.120.45.87"
4. Starting the HTTP service
 AT+HTTPIPINIT

AT+HTTTPARA="CID",1

5. HTTP GET request

AT+HTTTPARA="URL","http://example.com/data"

AT+HTTTPACTION=0

AT+HTTTPREAD

6. HTTP POST request

AT+HTTTPARA="URL","http://example.com/post"

AT+HTTTPDATA=20,5000

temperature=25&humidity=60

AT+HTTTPACTION=1

AT+HTTTPREAD

7. Closing the session

AT+HTTPTERM

AT+SAPBR=0,1

TCP/IP connection.

SIM900 also supports direct opening of TCP/IP sockets. The list of commands is given in table 2.

THE LIST OF COMMANDS

Commands	Explanation	Example/Answer
AT+CIPSHUT	Closes the previous session.	OK
AT+CIPSTATUS	Shows TCP/IP status	Answer: STATE: IP INITIAL
AT+CSTT="internet"	Sets APN settings	Internet for Azercell
AT+CIICR	Establishes a GPRS connection	OK
AT+CIFSR	Gets an IP address	Answer: 10.12.45.23
AT+CIPSTART="TCP", "server.com", "80"	Opens a TCP connection	OK / CONNECT OK
AT+CIPSEND	Sends information	GET /data HTTP/1.1

AT+CIPCLOSE	Closes the connection	OK
-------------	-----------------------	----

Table 2. The list of commands

5 UNIT FOR RECEIVING, FILTERING AND PROCESSING DATA ON RADON CONCENTRATION

Radon emanations form one of the most effective natural fields as earthquake precursors. This is the reason for organizing monitoring in almost all large regions of countries of the world with high seismic activity [9-18].

The highest concentration of radon is observed in soil and groundwater sources. The highest level of radioactivity is observed in groundwater in contact with radioactive crystalline fractured rocks - granites, gneisses, schists, diorites, clays. An automated radioecological station has been established in the western zone of Azerbaijan to study the problems of industrial waste in seismically active areas and to measure radon exhalation from the soil [3]. The conventional layout of the station is shown in the diagram below (Figure 3).

There are 1 and 3 are the radon radiometers measuring radon emission in soil; 2 is the radon radiometer measuring radon on the soil surface; 4 and 5 are the interface blocks for online transmission of measurement data; 6 is the computer for receiving and processing data.

Fig. 3. Scheme of measuring radon emission in soil and surface

As a result of studies conducted in seismically active regions of various countries, it has been found that radon, a radioactive gas that is released from geological rock layers and penetrates the air, is also considered one of the informative seismic forecast parameters as an indicator of rock changes during tectonic earthquakes. Due to its radioactive properties, radon is the most suitable for this type of research, since its volume activity level (Q) is quite easily determined in the environment [20].

6 PROTON MAGNETOMETER DATA RECEIVING UNIT

A proton magnetometer is a device used by geologists to measure and (sometimes) determine the Earth's magnetic field direction at a particular point in space. If several magnetic field measurements are taken over a large area of land using a coordinate grid, it is possible to determine the variations in the field caused by the presence of different types of rock in the subsurface. The proton magnetometer is widely used in exploration of some mineral deposits, as well as a trigger for earthquake prediction.

The Earth has a permanent magnetic field, which is generated by an electric current flowing through the molten material of the core. This current is created by the transfer of molten material up and down as a result of the heat released by the Earth's core. This process is complex and poorly understood.

The normal magnitude of the magnetic field on the Earth's surface ranges from 25 to 65 μT . It is this that causes the compass needle to turn north. The measurement of the field intensity on the surface can be affected by the presence of iron-containing rocks, as well as metallic iron, located at a shallow depth. The changes caused in this case are measured by geologists during exploration.

Figure 4 shows the developed electrical control circuit for the magnetometer.

The developed proton magnetometer measures the Earth's magnetic field with a resolution of 1 nT. This resolution is approximately 0.002% of the typical Earth's magnetic field. The proton magnetometer is also used to locate magnetic objects or materials in the ground. The proton magnetometer has a measurement range from 0 to 199.999 μT , the measurement error is $\pm 0.5\%$ or $\pm 0.001 \mu\text{T}$.

The proton magnetometer is sensitive to the slightest changes in the earth's magnetic field associated with the presence of magnetic materials in the ground. It is not affected by the environment, i.e. the signal of the proton magnetometer does not weaken due to the presence of dirt, water, stones, earth, which allows not only to measure the Earth's magnetic field with great accuracy, but also to find magnetic objects at great depth.

Due to the use of the quantum effect, proton magnetometers have important characteristics compared to other magnetometers. The proton magnetometer has no temperature drift of field measurements and no initial offset of readings. Precessing atoms modulate the intensity of the light beam. This is the basic principle of the proton magnetometer. As the momentum precesses, or rotates, around the magnetic field needle, it absorbs different amounts of light, thereby modulating the amplitude of beam.

The main characteristic of the magnetic field is the frequency of the free precession of protons around the lines of force of the measured field. Kerosene, poured into a cylindrical vessel, was used as a liquid containing protons. The useful signal is formed in two coaxial, counter-connected frameless coils placed in the vessel. To detect proton precession, the working substance is polarized (magnetized) by a strong magnetic field created by direct current in the same coils. The polarizing field should be approximately perpendicular to the measured field of the magnetic induction vector.

The MMP-203 magnetometer sensor was chosen as the primary magnetic transducer. It consists of a container with a working substance (kerosene) and a coil wound on it, providing magnetic polarization of the working substance, and subsequent removal of the precession frequency signal [21]. The coil parameters are selected in such a way as to create the largest possible polarizing field and effectively receive the nuclear magnetic

relaxation signal. It should be noted that the amplitude of the nuclear magnetic relaxation signal coming from the MMP-203 sensor is very small (about 500 nV).

Fig. 4. Electrical circuit for generating magnetometer signals.

To achieve a higher signal-to-noise ratio, the following technical solutions were used during development:

- the sensor, which is an inductance, is tuned using capacitors adjusted to resonance with the measured frequency of the precession signal;
- a transformer is used to match the low impedance sensor and the high input impedance precession amplifier;
- $3.9 \text{ nV} \cdot \text{Hz}^{-1/2}$ low-noise op-amps were used to develop a precession signal amplifier.

The above-mentioned precession amplifier block has together with the filter, its own noise at the level of 230 nV. First, the counter is started, clocked by a 13 MHz generator. After the measurement time of 0.6 s has elapsed and the final signal front has arrived, the counter value is stored and is used to calculate the precession frequency.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Thus, given paper presents the results of the development and research of an autonomous (robotic) measurement control complex based on Artificial Intelligence using the Machine Learning method. The complex is designed for simultaneous measurement of the concentration level of radioactive radon gas and the level of intensity of the Earth's

magnetic field with simultaneous analysis of seismic processes in the territory of Azerbaijan and neighboring regions, as well as the current state of solar activity. GPRS radio communication modem was developed to ensure communication with the Internet, to apply the machine learning method and communicate with the center. A software algorithm has been developed to control the complex, carry out measurements, and analyze the obtained data using the Machine Learning method. The purpose of the development and research is to study the correlations of measured physical quantities with seismic activity.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Azerbaijan Science Foundation – Grant № AEF-BQM-BRFTF-4-2024-5(53)-06/03/2-M-03.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

REFERENCES

1. Bayramov A.A., Abdullayev F.N., Suleymanov S.S., Karimova R.D., Safarov H.N., Rzayev E.A. Multifactor model for seismological research. Seismoprognozis observations in the territory of Azerbaijan. Vol.26, № 2, pp.28-33. (2024)
2. Moustavi S.M., Beroza G.C., Deep-learning seismology. Science, Vol. 377, No. 6607 (2022).
3. Bayramov A.A., Abdullayev F.N., Suleymanov S.S., Keramova A.A.. Development of an automated radioecological station for the purpose of studying the problems of industrial waste in seismically active areas. Materials of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference on the topic “ANAS-80”. Ganja. pp. 24-27. (2025).
4. Suxanov N.V. Development of a neural network model to predict the probability of an earthquake. Automation and modeling in design and management., №2(20), c.40-49. (2023).
5. Suleymanov S.S., Bayramov A.A., Abdullayev F.N. Study of seismic processes using AI technology. Current directions of development of information and communication technologies and control tools. Proceedings of 15-th International Scientific and Technical Conference. Xarkov, April 24 – 25, Volume 1: sections 1, 5. P.47. (2025).
6. Virt N. Algorithms and data structures. Moscow: DMK Press, 272p. (2010). (In Russ.)
7. Ismailov A.Kh., Bulenov B., Nauryzbaeva A.N. Intelligent software systems for big data analysis. Integration of science, education and production of an industrial state: in Proceeding of International scientific and practical conf. Nur-Sultan: Master Po ZhShS, pp.79–81. (2020).
8. Lowrie, William, 'The Effects of Solar Activity on the Geomagnetic Field', The Earth's Magnetic Field (Oxford, online ed., Oxford Academic, 22 June2023). <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192862679.003.0007>, accessed 15 July 2025.
9. Hartmann J., Levy J.K., Hydrogeological and Gasgeochemical Earthquake Precursors – A Review for Application. Natural Hazards 34, 279–304. (2005).
10. King C.-Y., Zhang W., Zhang Z., Earthquake-Induced Groundwater and Gas Changes. Pure and Applied Geophysics 163, 633–645. (2006).
11. Cicerone R.D., Ebel J.E., Britton J., A Systematic Compilation of Earthquake Precursors. Tectonophysics 476 (3–4) 371–396. (2009).

12. Ghosh D., Deb A., Sengupta R., Anomalous Radon Emission as Precursor of Earthquake. *Journal of Applied Geophysics* 69 (2), 67–81. (2009).
13. Jordan T.H., Gasparini P., Main I., Marzocchi W., Papadopoulos G., Sobolev G., Yamaoka K., Zschau J., Operational Earthquake Forecasting. State of Knowledge and Guidelines for Utilization. *Annals of Geophysics* 54 (4), 315–391. (2011).
14. Riggio A., Santulin M., Earthquake Forecasting: A Review of Radon as Seismic Precursor. *Bulletin of Geophysics and Oceanography* 56 (2), 95–114. (2015).
15. Woith H., Radon Earthquake Precursor: A Short Review. *The European Physical Journal Special Topics* 224, 611– 627. (2015).
16. Marennyy A.M., Kononenko D.V., Trufanova A.E. Radon survey in Chelyabinsk Oblast, Russia, in 2008–2011. Analysis of spatial variability of indoor radon concentration. *Radiatsionnaya Gygiena = Radiation Hygiene*. Vol. 13, No. 3. P. 51-67. (2020). (In Russian).
17. Tollefsen T, Cinelli G, Bossew P, Gruber V, De Cort M. From the European Indoor Radon Map Towards an Atlas of Natural Radiation. *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry*. 162(1-2): 129–34. (2014).
18. European Indoor Radon Map. (2020). Available from:
<https://remon.jrc.ec.europa.eu/About/Atlas-of-Natural-Radiation/Digital-Atlas/Indoor-radon-AM/Indoor-radon-concentration> (Accessed: 20 July 2020)
19. Seminsky K.Zh., Bobrov A.A., Correlation of Radon and Seismic Activity in the Baikal Rift Zone According to Emanation Monitoring Data. *Geodynamics & Tectonophysics* 15 (1), pp. 1-14. (2024).
20. Utkin, V.I.. Radon and the problem of tectonic earthquakes, *Soros educational journal*, volume 6, no. 12. pp. 64-70. (2000). (original in Russian)
21. Proton magnetometer MMP-203. 2019. <https://studfile.net/preview/9178987/page:3/>
 Accessed: 01.07.2025